

Partially Empty Sella Syndrome: Case ReportShashwat Arora¹, Ishita Singh², Subhi Mehta³¹Second Year Medical (MBBS) Student, Naraina Medical College and Research Centre, Kanpur, India²Second Year Medical (MBBS), Lala Lajpat Rai Memorial College, Meerut, India³Second Year Medical (MBBS), Lala Lajpat Rai Memorial College, Meerut, India

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Abstract:

Empty sella syndrome is characterized by the shrinkage or flattening of the pituitary gland. On an MRI scan, the pituitary gland appears invisible when it undergoes this process. This causes the pituitary gland region to appear as an "empty sella," though the sella is not truly empty as it is frequently filled with cerebrospinal fluid (CSF). The fluid that envelops the brain and spinal cord is called CSF. In empty sella syndrome, the pituitary is under strain because CSF has seeped into the sella turcica. As a result, the gland becomes flattened or shrunk.

Primary empty sella syndrome occurs when the arachnoid layer, which covers the brain protrudes into the sella and exerts pressure on the pituitary gland.

Keywords: Empty sella syndrome, neurology, pituitary gland, ischemia.

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Introduction

Empty sella syndrome is a condition in which there is pituitary gland shrinkage or flattening. The sella turcica, a saddle-shaped chamber at the base of the skull, houses the pituitary gland. An MRI scan reveals an empty sella when the pituitary gland shrinks or flattens, rendering it invisible.

This condition is known as "empty sella syndrome." A partially empty sella indicates that the MRI scan reveals only part of the pituitary gland. It typically presents in two forms: primary and secondary. Primary empty sella happens when fluid seeps through a hole in the diaphragmatic sella covering the pituitary and presses against the pituitary. Secondary empty sella syndrome is associated with pituitary gland damage from tumors, surgical or radiation therapy. [1]

Case Report

A 90-year-old male patient with a significant medical history of Type-2 Diabetes Mellitus, hypertension, and left ventricular hypertrophy presented to the emergency room early in the afternoon with severe confusion, lethargy, right-

sided drooping, weakness of right limbs, inability to walk, and slurred speech. Laboratory investigations revealed the following: Hemoglobin (Hb)- 11.8gm%, Packed Cell Volume (PCV)- 37.4%, Total Leukocyte Count (TLC)- 9680/cumm, Platelet count- 145000/cumm, INR-1.4, Blood Urea Nitrogen (BUN)-47mg/dl, Serum creatinine-1.9mg/dl, and Sodium/Potassium (Na/K)-137/4.1 mEq/L. The patient had the following symptoms from the past 7 days. He was then advised for MRI of head and 2D Echocardiography of heart. The patient's MRI revealed Partial Empty Sella Syndrome, with altered areas of signal intensities seen in pons, and evidence of recent infarcts. The sella turcica was filled with CSF with stretched elongated normal infundibular stalk.

The pituitary gland was thinned and flattened against the bony floor, consistent with partial empty sella syndrome. 2D Echocardiography showed left ventricular hypertrophy with posterior segment akinetic of left ventricle along with mild mitral valve regurgitation. No significant suspected clot or intracardiac masses were seen.

Figure1: Showing signs of Partially Empty Sella Syndrome

Figure 2: Zone of ischemia

Management and Treatment

The patient was started on Aspirin 75 mg with Clopidogrel 75 mg once daily, alongside Atorvastatin 80mg once daily, in addition to their usual medications for Type-2 Diabetes Mellitus.

The patient was advised for physiotherapy along with exercise and walking. The patient showed gradual improvement and Clopidogrel and Atorvastatin were weaned off.

The patient was called after 6 months for a routine check-up, showing normal behavior with restored function in the right-sided limbs.

Discussion

"Empty sella syndrome" is defined as a distinct anatomical and radiological phenomenon characterised by the expansion of the subarachnoid space into the sella turcica through an incompetent diaphragm sella.

Empty sella syndrome is often an incidental finding that occurs in patients with incompetent diaphragm sella, allowing the subarachnoid space to be driven into the sella under the influence of hydrostatic pressure and pulsatile CSF movement.

Patients with this condition may experience transient or persistent elevations in intracranial

pressure. It is more commonly observed in obese individuals. [2]

Pituitary gland compression may impair function, and traction on the optic chiasm and nerves may result in problems related to vision. When an empty sella develops in a person who has not had pituitary radiation or surgery, it may be considered primary while an empty sella discovered following such procedures is classified as secondary empty sella. [3]

Conclusion

Partially Empty Sella Syndrome (PES) is an uncommon clinical condition with a broad spectrum of symptoms, ranging from asymptomatic cases to severe presentations including hormone abnormalities or vision impairments. In this case report, the patient exhibited disorientation, slurred speech, drooping on the right side, and weak right limbs. Prompt diagnosis and treatment of PES are critical for preventing complications and improving the patient's quality of life. It is advised to conduct routine follow-ups to track any developments or modifications in the clinical presentation. This example adds to the increasing knowledge and awareness of PES by highlighting the significance of tailored patient care depending on the symptoms and diagnostic findings.

Ethical/Consent: Written consent was taken by the patient's family.

Transparency Statement: The author confirms that this manuscript is an honest, accurate, and

transparent account of the case reported. No significant aspects of the case have been omitted, and any discrepancies from the originally planned course of investigation or treatment have been fully disclosed. The author alone is responsible for the content and integrity of the work.

Authors' Contribution: Author-1 [Shashwat Arora], Author-2 [Ishita Singh] along with Author-3 [Subhi Mehta], were responsible for the conception, clinical management of the patient, data collection, analysis of diagnostic findings, and drafting of the manuscript. The authors also reviewed and approved the final version for submission.

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